

Personal Narratives: A Pedagogical Intervention in Writing

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Abstract

Among all the language skills, writing is one of the neglected skills; nevertheless, it is mostly abused in terms of its use as a key activity during “performance tasks”. This study devises a guide in writing among learners and motivates to improve their writing skills that recount the daily life’s experiences, thoughts, and feelings concerning to local and global concerns. A phenomenological research design was utilized and 36 participants were selected according to the qualifications’ set that undergone through Inclusion and exclusion process. Writing outputs were collected, analyzed, coded, categorized through the content analysis and the thematic approach; themes from these narratives were emerged. Semi-structured interview and focused-group discussion (FGD) were conducted to ensure the veracity and appropriateness of the guide question through a priori code. From this, guides were laid out according to style with a focus on foreshadowing, plot twist, revelation, unexpected events, flashback, red herring, Deus ex machine, characterization, diction, syntax, tone, voice, and a combination of the kinds of communication with narratives on the lead. Results revealed that personal narratives as a pedagogical intervention for learners when guided accordingly and taken with utmost care and confidentiality provide fluidity in the creation of ideas and concepts, development of learners’ logical and critical thinking, and develop the ability to reason out.

Keywords: Life experience, writing guide, writing style thematic approach, content analysis, Philippines

Introduction

Writing assesses person mastery - a complex macro skill that students do not value. In writing skills, the proper use of letters, symbols, numbers, sentences, mechanics, content organization, grammar, syntax, and vocabulary are overlooked. So, it was abandoned as a macro skill and writing was just done as a joke. On the other hand, at Carnegie Mellon University in the field of writing, the problems they also face are proper grammar, syntax, spelling, vocabulary, and expression of own feelings or opinions. Because of these problems, students become lazy, bored, disinterested. They cannot think of things they want to write, making writing jokes, diversity of perspectives. It will also be noted that students' writings are often done only with writings that are not given importance, students cannot explain their idea well, there is a lack of and extensive use of vocabulary, and incorrect rhetoric.

Of all the language skills, writing is the most difficult challenge for language teachers because students have less experience with written expression. It was proven by Gepila (2018), among the four macro skills, writing is considered to be the hardest to teach and learn.

This is in consonance with the study of students' writing experience by Saavedra and Barredo (2020). This is a lack of vocabulary in the target language; 2) difficulty in conveying and organizing ideas; 3) students' perception that writing is a difficult task; 4) lack of motivation and interest in writing, and 5) difficulty in spelling, grammar and sentence construction is the reason why many students have poor writing skills in English and Filipino So it is left as a macro skill and writing is just made as a joke.

In DepEd's Curriculum Guide (2015), the goal of teaching Filipino is to develop the communicative ability, comprehension skills, and literacy appreciation of students at the secondary level. Five macro skills will be developed - listening, reading, watching, speaking, and writing with the help of various approaches. Writing is a skill in the Filipino subject that will be given further discussion as a competency in the K to 12 curricula to prepare for and keep pace with the changes in the education system. Personal writing helps students to develop their competence in academic discourse when this writing strategy is also used. Launch it so that the writing has a clear meaning. If it is a genre of interpretation of an identity, it helps students to identify themselves as well as those they interact with. Personal writings are the tunnel of his beliefs, aspirations, feelings, and fiction. Of all the language skills, writing is the most difficult challenge for language teachers because students have less experience with written expression. In the field of education, teachers' guidance is very important in improving students' writing. The researcher thought of Personal Narrative in students' writing as a research topic to help them create and develop their ideas and concepts, develop their logical and critical thinking, and develop their ability to reason out and articulate their feelings. In this regard, most of those studies focused in the field of writing but no personal narrative as study was explored within the university as well as in the country.

Objectives of the Study

This research aimed to discover the writing styles of the students, analyze the writing of the students, and develop a pedagogical writing intervention for the students.

Methodology

Participants of the Study. The personal narratives of 36 participants were analyzed as a phenomenological study. It underwent content analysis and discovered the content of its writings. The samples were purposively chosen because of the following reasons: 1) They were personally interested in writing their narratives ; 2) The informants are enjoying writing their personal experiences.

Research Instrument. The research instrument used initial writing, after which personal narrative was used also then the semi-structured interview method. This was conducted to obtain the researchers' data from the participants from their independent responses and interaction. Developing the guide question as an instrument followed the process of de Guzman (2013) in his Interview Guide Development and it also underwent focus group discussion.

Data Collection. To gather all data, Interview Guide Development was used. These were as follows: 1) concept or layer of human experience; 2) definition; 3) a priori Codes; and 4) interview questions. The generated questions were analyzed, analyzed, and organized before the Aide Memoire was developed which is still based on de Guzman (2013). The contents of the Aide Memoir are as follows: A. Preamble: 1) Salutation- the brief profile of the researcher and the title of the study are introduced here. 2) Purpose- shared with the participant the purpose of the study and how to conduct the interview. 3) Motivation- mentioning the importance of learning as motivation for their participation. 4) Consent asking the participant if he or she would like to participate and respond to the study conducted. 5) Time- sharing with the participant how many hours or minutes will be spent in the interview. Research Instrument includes: 1) Respondents Robotfoto- taking the demographic profile of the participants needed in the study. 2) Interview Guide Questions. Lastly, Closing is composed of 1) Feedback- in this section the participant is asked if there are any clarifications and things to add to the responses; 2) Summary- gist of the interview conducted; 3) Remarks- acknowledging the participant for his or her participation

Data Analysis. This research is qualitative. The researcher used the Thematic Approach. By writing a personal experience of the students as reflected in the content analysis of the writing, as well as interviews were conducted with selected participants. Content analysis was also conducted in which the researcher analyzed the writings of the students. And there was an interview with the participants. It serves as validation. After that, the results of the collected data were analyzed, analyzed, and interpreted according to the coding, categorization, and general

theme in a thematic approach. All participants met the criteria set, including Grade 11, THNHS students, able to write Filipino, female, and male. According to Patton, (2002), there is no rule followed in taking sample size in the qualitative type of research. the sample number depends on what the researcher wants to know. Its purpose, what is there, what is needed, to still have credibility, and what to end with spare time and need. While only 10 took part in the interview, which was limited to 7 participants due to the saturation process of the data they have already provided. At the time, no new information came out was enough and this was used for the thematic approach.

Results and Discussion

From this, guides were clearly laid out according to style with a focus on foreshadowing, plot twists, revelation, unexpected events, flashbacks, red herring, deus ex machine, characterization, diction, syntax, tone, voice, and combination of the different types of communication.

1. Writing Styles of the Students

1.1. Foreshadowing the Consequences of Possible Events

In the style of the participants, it was seen that the writings used the expression of experiences. Something natural in this text. Inferring the consequence of what is likely to happen next or foreshadowing is a creative technique by the writer to foreshadow what will happen in the next consequence or something that will happen later.

Example. It also came to the point that I blamed for our situation being like that..."

Read in Kieffer's (2019) research cited by Bae et.al (2013) its use as part of writing a narrative to the student of their past helps to develop their abilities to think of possible happen in the next.

1.2. Plot Twist

This is a fun thing because it motivates how a person feels when they write the sudden changes in the whole event in the story. The events in the story serve as a guide for the readers to believe something that is often seen in the end, an unexpected event in the change taking place in the plot.

So, in the idea of Witte (1994), it is said that this narrative style focuses on the plot which motivates the readers to get the attention to the climax events in a story.

1.3. Revelation

Revealing the full courage of their personality, the pain felt, love, and many others is a great help to better understand themselves and situations faced in life. This type of writing has made the outline colorful.

Ex.1 "I found out from my brother that there is My mother has cancer. "

Gonzales (2015) proved that effectively launching this style to express feelings, and not be afraid to share personality will be the way for a student to become an effective writer. That means reality is being the same as what you think or whatever is in mind in what circumstances things are.

1.4. Announcing Something Unexpected Happens

Example: Because my siblings since they graduated from school instead of looking for a job, they are just a burden to mama and papa so now they have no benefit in their lives and they only forbid me those who don't I have a boyfriend in case you had a BF last year."

It will be noticed that the participant used in his writing that it came out of heart and style in this type of outline. Not all participants were able to use this style so my research found only two. The use of this style in personal narrative has been substantiated by Brown (2012) and has presented the eventualities in a real-life story.

1.5. Flashback

In the writing style, let the reader guess what might happen. Allow them to separate a flashback or some evidence or dialogue that is clean and clues to something. When the outline change happens, readers should be surprised again, looking at what else happened when everything was put together. One may have flashbacks when we think of a year and remember some memory that that person was part of lives, or one may look at something and think about when we got it, or why it was important. Many different things in daily lives can trigger flashbacks, and one does not always know it.

Authors use flashbacks in their works for many different reasons. A major factor is to fill in the elements of one or more-character backstories. Flashbacks help the reader understand certain motivations that are otherwise unclear or give recognition in other ways. Looking back on participants' pasts can bring a smile to their laughing lips, painful memories of the past, and experiences that gave strength, and endurance to our will. Of the three participants, they varied in style the first was in the form of thrill. The color of their writing appeared more as a kind of transformation.

Example. “Year two thousand seven (2017) I took a chance in Manila March 18, 2019. I first met him on Facebook. I found out his name”.

According to Belvez, et. al (2001) the function of retrospect is to generate hope in the minds of the readers about what might happen next, thus adding dramatic tension to a story. It is intentionally employed to create excitement in mystery novels or writings, usually by providing red herrings- to distract readers, here the vigilance that can make extraordinary and bizarre events is predicted in advance so that readers will prepare a psyche for them.

1.6. Red Herring

In literature, this fall is often used in detective or suspension novels to cultivate readers or characters and encourage them to draw wrong conclusions.

Example 1 “I experienced beatings from my new classmates. They dragged me to the C.R and locked suddenly...

Master Class (2019) proved that the use of this style is a way to attract and entice the interest of the readers, by hinting at explanations that may not be true, the use of this technique involves the readers believing a wrong conclusion about a plot. When the participants have finished reading, they will be surprised at the reality and enjoy the delusion and have learned something useful about the event and character.

1.7. Deus ex machine (God from the Machine)

According to Jhonson (2007). The literary device of Deus ex Machina originated in the tradition of Greek drama to use a machine to lower or lift the characters who played their gods up to the stage.

Ex.1 “You don’t have to choose between the two of us as long as you always love me. Pleased keep me on your heart. Don’t be held by someone, don’t be dictated.

It also emerged in the writing of the participant’s experiences of the use of this style. It may be that emerging new personnel can help with severe problems through unexpected personnel, objects, or circumstances. The keys to the problem are not shown or introduced at the beginning of the story, instead, it is all of a sudden. In life, we are held by any circumstances.

Prdyono, (2007). If an inexplicable concept or a divine character is introduced into a storyline to resolve its conflict and obtain an interesting outcome, The explanation given by critics for this view is the writer's sudden action of random, unsupportable, and unbelievable twists or changes with the intent of having an ending, highlighting the inherent shortcomings of the plot. Therefore, it is indisputable, and often a form of literary material.

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1.8. Characterization

This type of characterization is also known as implicit characterization. While it takes more time to produce a character through indirect recognition, it often leaves a deeper impression on the reader than direct statements about what a character is. Here are examples of indirect personality.

Example. "Hazel sighed as to whether she was going to join our group of friends. She really should have joined. But we don't know why she doesn't like us what exactly she saw in our group."

Example "As Jeff walked, he was paralyzed, he carefully glanced at him, then, he suddenly stood up as if nothing had happened."

Subsequently, in the study by Mayer (2007). People have become more interested in why people do things and the way they react rather than what happens. The literature reflects this change. However, that is not to say that works written before the 19th-century lack recognition.

1.9. Diction

Diction is the choice of words based on the situation: happy, sad, scary, enthralling, and so on. The combination of these two helps writers to develop tone, emotion, and atmosphere in texts to arouse the spirit of interest of the readers. *"I can't explain the pain I'm feeling. Despite what is happening in my life."* In this example, it will be noticed that what he feels is incomprehensible. Mixed feelings are proof that in someone's life we lead to anxiety over our feelings caused by our life experiences.

1.10. Imagination

Sight: The sunset was the most gorgeous they had ever seen; the clouds were covered with pink and gold.

Smell: The scent of her hair reminded me of my late mother.

According to Aguire (2014) cited by Gonzales (2105), this type of writing is artistic. the focus here is on the imagination of the writer, although the work being written may be fictional or non-fictional. It also aims primarily to arouse the imagination, in addition to arousing the emotions of the readers. This is the kind of writing in literature. Therefore, writing poetry, novels, short fiction, plays, and short essays can be classified under this category.

1.11. Point of View

This narrator is often the protagonist of the story, and this point of view allows the reader access to the character's inner thoughts and reactions to what has occurred. All actions are processed through the narrator's perspective, and therefore, this type of narrator may be unreliable. Choosing to write from an unreliable first point of view allows the reader to find out what is truth and what is an invention on the part of the narrator of the narrative perspective.

1.12. Syntax

The formation of sentences in a language in which in Filipino, the subject can precede the predicate and it can also be reversed. Most of the sentences formed are in standard order. The predicate precedes the verb. Some of

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the sentences formed are: *"I was just shocked by what happened in our area."* *"I loved my parents but..."* But some sentences precede the subjects before the predicates as follows: *"His eyes, hay..."* *"I dream of him but, nothing..."* In these examples, it can be seen that the participants also use two types of formation according to the syntax requirement. It can also be seen that they still know their syntax skills.

1.13. Tone

"I was hurt, at least I got my revenge, that's not what's important but education. It doesn't matter, there are more there." In this example, we can see that the writer of his personal experience feels sad and hopeful.

Tone refers to the writer's behavior. It can be informal, serious, sadistic, sad, and motivating. Emotions, tone, purpose, and perspective are discovered in the writing of a text or essay. They can be identified by the words they use in the text. (a) Emotion: This refers to the reader's attitude in the text. It can be joy, sadness, anger, hatred, fear, admiration, astonishment, hope, despair, courage, apprehension, frustration, annoyance, and other emotions or feelings. (b.) Tone; refers to the attitude of the reader's creation of the text. Some works do the trick and present a serious subject. The tone can be joking or sarcastic, happy or sad, serious or satirical, used to show the true color of the experience. Thus, in *Style, Tone, and Mood*, by Duarte (2013), emotion or mood is the general feeling or emotion generated in the reader. the author evokes the emotion of the reader through selected words at the level of detail in the act. The tone of the writer in his speech can be identified whether he has a positive or negative outlook or perspective on the subject.

1.14. Voice

The voice in literature is a format of the narrator's storytelling. It is intimate when a writer puts himself into words and gives the feeling that the character is truly human, providing a specific message the writer wants to convey. In simple words, it is an individual writing style or point of an author's pen. It is only in the voices of the writer's writing that it can be seen what a person's character is throughout the story. It is only in the way he speaks or narrates that we know what kind of person wrote a story. *"Sometimes, I don't go for a walk and I envy those, my friend because they are allowed to take walks. But it's okay, I can help at home."*

1.15. Symbols

Symbols represent these larger ideas or characteristics. For example, an author may use a particular color that in itself is no more than one color, but hints at a deeper meaning. *Angels brought me here, to be with you always.* According to Aguire (2014) cited by Gonzales (2105), this type of writing is artistic. the focus here is on the imagination of the writer, although the work being written may be fictional and non-fictional. It also aims primarily to arouse the imagination in using symbols. This is the kind of writing in literature. Therefore, writing poetry, novels, short stories, plays, and short essays can be classified under this category.

1.16. Discourse Combination

The participant used descriptive writing mixed with her narrative. A text is descriptive if it contains information related to the physical characteristics of an object, place, or even the characteristics of a person or group of people. It usually responds to the question, "What?" So if the two examples are examined it answers the question of what the participants used. But it helped the participants to color the entirety of their writing.

"As soon as you get off the bus you will hear the noise of people and cars, you will see young people begging, running in the street."

"Despite the happiness, is there a partner in sadness. You can only feel sad for other people because of their ridicule of sex"

Conclusions

The writing style is very important. Its use helps students to be creative, release emotion and be truthful to fully examine and understand the life of an individual by writing using Exit style. A personal narrative is effectively launched in writing and it has been instrumental in developing a handbook that serves guide in writing. There are different writing styles to be seen, and the way they write is even more obvious. The style that emerged is the inference of possible consequences (foreshadowing), plot twist, flashback, red herring, unexpected event, Deus ex machine, characterization (characterization), syntax, diction, tone, voice symbolism, imagination, point of view, and a combination of narrative with various types of expression. Revelation and the proclamation of an unexpected event also appear as sub components of the change in structure.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations after analyzing the results and forming conclusions of the study.

1. Stakeholders may consider the following for helping achieve writing proficiency and bring it closer to children who are bored with writing especially those with difficulties.
2. The use of personal narrative as an option and motivation in developing writing can be re-taught. written output. It is good to have a writing guide, to keep in mind and to include a proposals as the output of this research can be used as a basis.
3. The guide is more useful if it is validated by more experts. It can now be distributed to schools that are having difficulty with effective writing.
4. It is suggested to further explore its contribution to other forms of expression especially written, such as descriptive, argumentative, and expository. Also, aim to apply personal narrative to other macro skills such as reading, viewing, and speaking for more comprehensive data.

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